

ASPECTS OF PROFESSIONAL GROWTH OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN MEDICINE

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Annotation. *This article is devoted on the value of English in medicine. English is the lingua franca of the medical world providing common ground for international medical professionals to share knowledge, collaborate on research, and discuss best practice. This topic is relevant today, when humanity has expanded its information and territorial boundaries.*

Keywords: *EhGLISH for doctors, English in medicine, learning English, medical English.*

In today's world, where the borders of different countries are becoming easier to overcome, especially for professionals in the medical field, importance of English is significantly increasing. Globalization and accelerated exchange of information require knowledge of the language of international communication and, in particular, its special features and the use of terminology in the medical professions. Consequently, it becomes urgently necessary to acquire reading skills and a good understanding of the medical literature in the English language for progressing to the level required for communication with colleagues from the USA, the UK, Australia, Israel and other countries known for their significant achievements in the development of medicine. Why should a doctor know English? First of all, it may seem that the doctor's knowledge of English is not the key aspect in professional growth. In fact, if you aim at the constant improvement of skills and want to work in a prestigious clinic, and even more so, to cooperate with your foreign colleagues, you must know English. Let's see how the knowledge of English helps a doctor.

1. The doctor who speaks English is better aware of current trends in medicine.

Knowing English, you can freely read foreign medical journals, most of the modern books on medicine; get acquainted with publications in the English language on medical websites. Moreover, of course, in terms of volume and relevance, such information significantly compares favorably with the information available in Russian or Uzbek. Knowledge of the English language allows you to improve skills continuously and keep abreast of advanced diagnostic and treatment methods.

But why English? Because of the fact that scientific publications, primarily, are available for a wide range of readers just in English, and it can take a lot of time before they will be translated into Russian or Uzbek. In the scientific community, and not only, English is the language of international communication.

2. Knowing English, you can get or continue medical education abroad. If you are only going to be a doctor, you may enter a foreign university, and proficiency in English is one of the main conditions for the implementation of your plans. You do not need a large sum of money to study at a foreign university. There are various training programs for prospective students, so that you can study abroad without spending too much money, but without knowledge of foreign languages, it is impossible. Primarily, we are talking about English. If you are already a general practitioner and would like to grow professionally, it is possible to do an internship in a foreign clinic, a refresher course and advanced professional training abroad to participate in international research projects in the field of medicine. But for this, you will also need knowledge of the English language.

3. Knowledge of English will allow you to participate in medical conferences abroad. Prestigious clinics are interested in ensuring their physicians' participation in various scientific events abroad, such as conferences devoted to medical issues. Therefore, if you work in a clinic or in research institute, you have the opportunity to make a business trip abroad, but for this, you need a good knowledge of English, because such events are usually held in English.

4. Knowledge of English will allow you to work in a team with foreign specialists. Many domestic clinics cooperate with foreign medical institutions, invite foreign experts to work or carry out consultations in difficult cases, to make a diagnosis jointly or to determine the methods of treatment of patients. In addition, doctors speaking English fluently, are invited to participate in international clinical trials

5. Knowledge of English allows the doctor to have an appointment with foreign patients in private clinics. Probably, if you work in a small clinic of a small town, only your compatriots will seek your medical advice. But, for example, in a private clinic of the capital city, cooperating with insurance companies, you can have foreign patients. If you plan to work or undertake an internship abroad, you cannot do it without knowledge of the English language.

6. To know English is prestigious. Regardless of your occupation, whether you are a doctor or another specialist, if you can speak foreign languages, you will be considered more valuable asset in any company cooperating with foreign partners or not. Knowledge of the English language says about your education, emphasizes that you are a modern, open personality, aimed at self-improvement.

As you can see, a doctor has many reasons to learn English. The level of English must be quite high. The doctor must be familiar with medical terminology, be able to read and fully understand even the most difficult medical texts, have listening comprehensive skills, communicate with colleagues from other countries. The doctor should speak English clearly, so that the other person can understand every word, including medical “jaw-breakers”. Of course, all the doctors know Latin, it helps avoid any confusion in medical terms, but a living language is still necessary for dialogue. Even more, you cannot talk to foreign patients using the Latin language.

Having analyzed all the above-mentioned points, we concluded that the English language was very important in medicine. This is the language that connects the knowledge and achievements of different countries, makes it possible to transfer the experience, skills and knowledge. In our time, every physician should know Medical English.

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